

**SPEECH ETIQUETTE AS A MEANS OF INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION
(ON THE EXAMPLE OF THE FRENCH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES).**

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Abstract. *This article highlights the national and cultural features of speech labels in French and Uzbek languages.*

Keywords: *etiquette, speech etiquette, French and Uzbek language, culture, norms.*

РЕЧЕВОЙ ЭТИКЕТ КАК СРЕДСТВО МЕЖКУЛЬТУРНОГО ОБЩЕНИЯ (НА ПРИМЕРЕ ФРАНЦУЗСКОГО И УЗБЕКСКОГО ЯЗЫКОВ).

Аннотация. *В данной статье освещаются национально-культурные особенности речи. этикетки на французском и узбекском языках.*

Ключевые слова: *этикет, речевой этикет, французский и узбекский язык, культура, нормы.*

The word "etiquette" (from the French *étiquette* - label, label) definition is divided as a set of rules of conduct relating to attitude towards people (dealing with others, forms of address and greetings, behavior in public places, manners and clothing).

The norms of etiquette are consensual in nature; they are, as it were, presuppose an agreement on what is considered accepted in human behavior, and which is not accepted. In this regard, there is an extraordinary diversity of rules etiquette among different peoples, determined by the special conditions of their historical development. Throw a gnawed bone to another person, with our point of view is to humiliate him. Indeed, etiquette is a form of social control over behavior of each person, and violation of etiquette causes certain sanctions. They can be different: starting from condemning amazement and ending with a fine for violating public order.

The term "etiquette" means form, behavior, rules courtesy and politeness accepted in a particular society. England and France is usually called "the classic countries of etiquette." Speech etiquette is part of culture, without which humanity cannot live can carry out his daily activities.

He expresses the language the istic side of language and at the same time reveals human culture special relations through the use of linguistic means. At the same time, the researchers set as their goal to reveal the general language basic principles of the functioning of speech etiquette in different types of speech activity, consider issues of style, genre, types of speech and general language, grammatical patterns and features of language use kovical means, determine the specifics of the use of speech etiquette in various spheres of human activity.

Speech etiquette has been the subject of study by scientists in Uzbekistan.

It should be noted that in line with the scientific research carried out by us about the search, the dissertation works of E.M. were completed. Gurtueva (1986), D .A. Babakhanova (1987), R.M. Avezdzhanova (1991), B.Kh. Rakhmatillaeva (1992).

Linguists note that speech etiquette for many years Ekov developed ethical norms of relationships and cultural communication between people. Peoples have always strived to generalize the best traits you and the forms of relationships, critically evaluate and condemn each

other. This became the basis for the development of speech etiquette and formulas for noun statements.

Let us pay attention to an excerpt from the book by Anne and Serge Golon "Put to Versailles": Recently, this woman is in the luxurious palace of King Louis XIV. She was one of the most beautiful queens. He was fascinated by her beauty under the ardent gaze of the royal servants, this woman is very beautiful he was dancing while wearing a dress. More recently, this woman was one of the most brilliant ladies of the luxurious court of the young King Louis XIV.

She danced there in a beautiful dress, surrounded by the fiery gazes of the courtiers x, mesmerized by her beauty. It was Angélique de Sancé de Montelou.

Il y avait peu de temps encore, cette femme avait été l'un des plus beaux ornements de la luxury cour du jeune roi Louis XIV. Elle y avait dansé en robe de drap d'or, entourée du feu admirateur des regards qu'attirait sa beauté. Elle s'appelait Angélique de Sancé de Monteloup.

It says here that this woman is one of the most brilliant ladies of a luxurious court, which means she is the wife of a rich gentleman ra of that time, which is a special socially etiquette sign.

A light whistle drew her attention to the gutter. Suddenly you Jumping from there, Barcarolle appeared. - Excuse me, marquise, for that that I left on the sly without saying goodbye.

I ran for my friend Fanin "Wooden butt," said the dwarf, taking a deep breath.

Un sifflement léger attira son attention vers l'embouchure d'un égout.

Surgissant de l'orifice, le nain Barcarole reparut. — Pardonnez-moi de vous avoir faussé compagnie, marquise, j'étais allé quérir mon ami Janin-Cul-de-Bois.

Analysis of this passage shows that the author uses one of traditional formulas of speech etiquette, expressed by the phrase "I'm sorry "Eat me", "meni kechiring", "pardonnez-moi".

Business etiquette in France largely requires compliance with formalities. A common form of greeting is light handshake.

Meetings should be arranged in advance. Punctuality is seen as a sign of politeness.

However, the general rule is: The higher the status of the guest, the more lateness is allowed.

For the French, education and the general level of knowledge, erudition. They are rightfully proud of their culture good acquaintance with history, philosophy, art are highly valued.

Accordingly, gifts that meet intellectual needs or sense of beauty will be well received (for example, books or art albums). However, in a business environment, exchanging gifts is not especially accepted.

The manifestation of individuality and originality is extremely important for French. They prefer to conduct business meetings and negotiations precisely in French, even if they themselves speak other languages. Great importance is given to rhetoric, the ability to logically correctly express one's thoughts in following sequence: thesis, antithesis, synthesis. Much attention they pay attention to details, their precision. Tactical techniques when conducting negotiations can be extremely diverse.

In general, in our opinion, speech etiquette is an important means our national culture. It plays a huge role in preserving formulas of speech communication. Speech etiquette is a very interesting topic problem, and it must be remembered that the correctness and accuracy of speech.

Some uses of linguistic means in the compared languages are the main factors in the expression of incentive statements.

REFERENCES

1. Large linguistic dictionary. Starichenok V.D. Rostov-n/D. 2008.
2. Vvedenskaya L.A. "Russian language and culture of speech". M. 2002.
3. Goldin V.E. Speech and etiquette. M.: "Enlightenment", 1983.
4. Maslova V.A. Linguoculturology. M.: Academy. 2001.
5. Formanovskaya N.I. Russian speech etiquette: linguistic and methodical aspects. M.: 1982.